

THE SIGNIFICANCE OF DIDACTIC GAMES IN ASSESSING STUDENTS' KNOWLEDGE

¹Turakulova M.N., ²Ruzikulova N.A.

¹Master's student of Uzbekistan-Finland Pedagogical Institute

²Associate Professor of Uzbekistan-Finland Pedagogical Institute

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Abstract. *The article provides information on the assessment of students during the lesson and the benefits of mental didactic games. Through the use of didactic games in the teacher's pedagogical activity, it is possible to increase the level of knowledge of students, introduce them to the environment, develop their interest in learning, and teach them certain methods of mental activity.*

Keywords: *lesson, mental didactic games, evaluation, biology, plant, animal, organ.*

Today, it is becoming one of the urgent issues to pay special attention to general education schools in our country. Various measures are being taken in order to increase the knowledge levels of teachers, to further develop their teaching methods and technologies. One of such activities is the introduction of unconventionality in the lessons, increasing the students' attention and interest in the lesson, and increasing their involvement in the lesson process. One of the most important issues to be addressed is the ability to assess all students in one lesson. At first glance, it may seem a bit impossible to do all this at the same time, that is, in the course of a 45-minute lesson. But it can be done. We all know that in today's century, various methods and technologies of teaching are being developed and we are using them widely. Cooperative learning technology, modular learning technology, design technology, PISA tests and assignments, etc. can be examples of this. There is one more such important technology that the demand for it is increasing more and more. This is the technology of using didactic games in the lesson. The use of didactic games in the course of the lesson has several advantages. For example, repetition of the first topic is unconventional and gives a special energy to the lesson process; secondly, students' logical development grows, gives students the opportunity to think freely, the teacher's creative approach to the lesson increases, and finally, one of the most important aspects is that it provides an opportunity for the teacher to evaluate all students. In this case, the teacher is required to choose a game that provides such an opportunity. Because there are many types of didactic games and they are diverse. There are games that can be played as a team, played individually, and played in small groups. Below we present to your attention several games that allow you to evaluate all the students in the class in one lesson. These games were used in the 7th-8th grades of the 21st general education school of Toyloq district of Samarkand region and positive results were obtained. As a result, students' activity in the course of the lesson and their interest in science increased, the skills of analyzing theoretical knowledge and mutual healthy competition were formed. With the help of mental didactic games, it is possible to have the opportunity to fully assess the students of the class at the same time, and below are some examples of mental didactic games.

Game "Vertebrates and Invertebrates".

This game is for 7th grade students and the schedule is presented below. Pupils should color the cell with the names of the animals in the table according to which type they correspond to and write whether the circulatory system is open or closed. For example, an earthworm belongs

to the type of invertebrates and has a closed circulatory system. Therefore, the box with the name of the earthworm is painted with a blue pencil and the word "closed" is written next to it.

VERTEBRATES	INVERTEBRATES
Earthworm	closed
Scorpion	open
Eagle	closed
Shark	
Crab	
Gavial	
Water slime	
Ostrich	
Osminog	
Salamander	

"Kahoot" game

The name of this game is derived from a game called "Kahoot" which is played online on the internet. In the game, each student is given cards in the form of , , , , (10 each) and questions. Each question has the same answer options as in the above forms. Which form of the answer option is correct, students write the number of the question on a blank paper and stick the appropriate form on the paper. At the end of the game, the matching of the forms with the answers is checked. For example, questions can be made as follows:

- In which zone of the root are hairs located?
 sucker; - grower
 the conductor; - divider
- What performs the function of transport in the stem?
 conducting pipes; root hairs
 sieve tubes; conducting and sieve tubes
- How many zones does the root consist of?
 three ; two; four; five
- What is the evaporation of water from a plant leaf?
 -diffusion transpiration
 - the osmotic phenomenon of respiration

"Find the excess" game

This game is designed for 8th grade students, where a table and five words are given in each of its rows. Among these words, there is one extra word that does not match the other four words. Students have to find this redundant word and color the inside of that box with a colored pencil.

PLASTIDA	CYTOPLASM	GOLGI COMPLEX	LYSOSOMA	NUCLEUS
PROTEIN	WATER	CARBON WATER	NUCLEIC ACID	FAT
BLOOD	LYMPH	NEURON	SHARE	BONE
LIVER	KIDNEY	HEART	LUNGS	NOSE
HEART	THROAT	LARYNX	BRAIN	LUNGS

STOMACH	LIVER	HEART	INTESTINES	GALL BLADDER
MAMMARY GLANDS	SECONDARY GLAND	SALIVARY GLANDS	STOMACH WALL	SEBATE GLANDS
GASTROINTESTINAL GLAND	EPIPHYSIS	ADRENAL GLAND	SECONDARY GLAND	HYPOPHYSIS
THYROXINE	THIAMIN	THYMOSIN	MELATONIN	ADRENALINE

"Choose the matching words" game

The condition of the game is as follows. The teacher distributes a paper with text and a paper with words to each student. Some words of the text are omitted. Students fill in the blanks of the text using the words written on the paper, that is, they have to place the appropriate words on the paper correctly in the text. For example, as follows.

Text:

The kidney surface is smooth, it will be in the shade. the inner side of the kidney is more concave. the cavity in it is called In the cross-section of the kidney, its exterior is dark and leaking internal floors are available. Renal calyx is the interior of the kidney is located in the it gradually narrows and passes to the urinary tract. It consists of two flutes in the form of 2 cylinders. is the structural and functional unit of the kidney. Urine collects in The diameter of the urethra is The size of the bladder reaches The length of each nephron is Is

Keywords: renal medulla, 6-8 mm, medulla, light brown, urinary bladder, 50-55 mm, renal hilum, renal calyx, ureter, nephron, 500-700 cm³, renal cortex.

In conclusion, it can be said that the use of mental didactic games in the course of the lesson develops students' logical thinking skills, and the above types give the teacher the opportunity to work with all students.

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